

Scattering Balance Approach to Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics

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In a series of notes, we argued a time reversal elastic scattering balance may yield the equilibrium number distribution for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac (FD), Bose-Einstein (BE) and other generalized cases. This approach makes no use of ensembles, entropy or partition functions. For electrons in an atom, however, it seems there are interactions with photons as opposed to electron-electron scattering, yet temperature equilibrium may still apply. In this note, we try to apply an interaction approach to quantum systems and examine if it matches traditional treatments, especially those related to calculating spatial density.

Two Body Time Reversal Elastic Scattering Balance

The scattering approach uses the elastic two-body reaction $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((1a)), together with a “modified density type” probability collision balance equation:

$g(f(e_1))g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3))g(f(e_4))$ ((1b)) where $g=1$ for the MB case, $f/(1-f)$ for FD and $f/(1+f)$ for BE statistics. Taking \ln of ((1b)) and linking to ((1a)) yields:

$$\ln(g(f(e))) = -1/T (e-u) \quad ((2))$$

One may proceed to define a Kaniadakis entropy density $(1) = \int df \ln(g(f))$ and then obtain a grand canonical partition function using $E-TS+uN$, although this is not necessary to obtain $f(e)$ which follows from ((2)).

Quantum Situation

Temperature equilibrium ideas have been applied both to electrons in an atom and nucleons in large nuclei. Traditionally, it seems the idea of an ensemble of systems, e.g. atoms or nuclei, (similar to that used in classical statistical mechanics) is applied to create a canonical distribution. The canonical distribution weight $\exp(-E/T)/Q$ for a system in an ensemble follows from maximizing (with approximations such as large m_i) (2):

$$M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots) \text{ where } m_i = \text{the number of systems in an ensemble with energy } E_i \quad ((3a))$$

If one applies this idea to either electrons in an atom or nucleons, both fermions, one often sees in the literature:

$$\text{density}(r) = \text{Sum} \exp(-E_i/T)/Q \{ \text{determinant} | \phi_i(1)(r_1) \phi_i(2)(r_2) \dots \}^2 \text{ with the } r_i \text{ vectors being permuted.} \quad ((3b))$$

Here Q is the normalization of $\exp(-E_i/T)$ which is proportional to the canonical partition function.

Each determinant represents exactly N fermions, but may have an overall different energy:

$E_i = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i \text{ for each determinant.}$

The weight $\exp(-E_i/T)$ seems to be used on the basis of an ensemble argument. Thus, one does not examine interactions which occur in the system for this derivation. We try to apply an interaction approach.

Interaction Approach applied to Quantum Mechanics

Consider solving the Schrodinger equation for an electron in an atom. This yields single particle energy levels. It is known from experiment an electron in a level above the ground level may “decay” to the ground level emitting a photon or absorb a photon and move to a higher energy level, yet these interactions with photons are not formally part of the solution of the time independent Schrodinger equation. They nevertheless govern important physics of the atom. We argue interactions are key for justifying a temperature equilibrium in quantum mechanics. For the case of electrons in an atom, however, it seems one may not simply apply scattering arguments i.e. ((2)) as one does not have scattering electrons.

Even without two body scattering, one may argue that for equilibrium, overall energy must be conserved, particle number be conserved (for the case considered here) and the average number of particles in each state must be constant. It seems one may consider the idea of an “average” because one may have either 1 or 0 electrons in an atomic energy state (ignoring spin). Thus, considering an ensemble of atoms seems to make sense. In some atoms, there will be an electron in state e_i , in others not. One way to balance interactions is to consider:

Probability(electron drops from e_1 to e_2) = Probability(electron rises from e_2 to e_1)

Or: $f(e_1) = f(e_2)q(\text{photon } e_1-e_2)$ ((4))

Here, $f(e_i)$ is the number of electrons in state e_i (across the systems in the ensemble) and $q(\text{photon } e_1-e_2)$ the probability for an electron to absorb a photon. If the balance ((4)) holds, overall throughout the ensemble, every electron decaying from e_1 to e_2 is replaced with one rising from e_2 to e_1 . Taking the ln of ((4)) yields:

$\ln(f(e_1)) = \ln(f(e_2)) + \ln(q)$ ((5)) A solution to ((5)) is: $f(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ and $q = \exp(-(e_1-e_2)/T)$

This approach, however, does not account for the Pauli exclusion principle, so ((4)) is rewritten as:

$f(e_1) [1-f(e_2)] = f(e_2) [1-f(e_1)] q(\text{photon } e_1-e_2)$ ((5)) Then:

$\ln[f(e_1)/(1-f(e_1))] = -(e-u)/T$ ((6)) is a solution, and this yields the FD distribution

Thus, the Fermi-Dirac distribution may be obtained using an interaction approach in an atom and the idea of ensembles. This is interesting because it seems to imply one may model electrons in an atom by a Fermi gas if the inter-level spacing is equal. The idea of describing nucleons in a nucleus by a Fermi gas has been used successfully in the literature, although with nucleons, one may be able to apply two body scattering directly.

Spatial Density

The traditional canonical weight approach used in quantum statistical mechanics yields the spatial density ((3b)). How may one apply the interaction approach above to obtain a density and does it match ((3b))? Given one has many atoms in an ensemble, the density should be of the form:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ Weight}(i) \text{ determinant(corresponding to arrangement of single particle states } i) \quad (5)$$

Thus, one must determine the weights. Consider a simple example, two electrons with three energy states e_1, e_2 and e_3 . (In general, statistical mechanics is to apply to large n systems, but that does not seem to affect the interaction balance arguments. It may be more applicable to fluctuations (i.e. from a grand canonical partition function).

Then, an atom may have the following states:

$$(1 \ e_1 \ 0 \ e_2 \ 1 \ e_3 \ \text{weight } N_1) \ (0 \ e_1 \ 1 \ e_2 \ 1 \ e_3 \ \text{weight } N_2) \ (1 \ e_1 \ 1 \ e_2 \ 0 \ e_3 \ \text{weight } N_3) \quad (6)$$

For the N_3 case, one cannot have e_1 drop to e_2 or vice versa because of the Pauli principle. From the interaction picture:

$$f(\text{FD})(e_1) / f(\text{FD})(e_2) = (N_1 + N_3) / (N_2 + N_3) \ \text{and} \ f(\text{FD})(e_1) / f(\text{FD})(e_3) = (N_1 + N_3) / (N_1 + N_2) \quad (7)$$

Here $f(\text{FD})$ is the Fermi-Dirac distribution. Solving where $f=f(\text{FD})$:

$$N_1 = x \quad N_3 = x \left[\frac{f_1/f_3 + f_2/f_1 - 1}{1 - f_2/f_3 + f_1/f_3} \right]$$

$$N_2 = x \left[\frac{f_2/f_1 + (f_2/f_3 + 2 - 2f_2/f_1 - f_1/f_3)}{1 - f_2/f_3 + f_1/f_3} \right] \quad (8)$$

One may proceed to normalize using $N_i / (N_1 + N_2 + N_3)$.

These do not appear to be the canonical distribution weights ($\exp(-E/T)$) of ((2)).

Comparison of the Two Approaches

One may ask why there seems to be a difference between the two approaches. If one did not have determinants squared and used a grand canonical partition function, one would obtain an $f(\text{FD})(e_i)$ distribution for each e_i . If one replaces $\exp(-E_i/T)/Q$ in ((3b)) with the grand canonical approximation $\exp(-E_i/T + uN_i/T)$ (adding determinants to represent N_i electrons) and integrates the determinants squared, each integrating to 1 (if normalized in such a way), then it seems one has grand canonical partition function approach which yields $N = \sum_i f(\text{FD})(e_i)$. In general calculations in the literature, however, the canonical and not the grand canonical partition function is used. It seems the Fermi-Dirac distribution may result even from the canonical distribution, but only for large particle number as shown in (3). Both the canonical and grand canonical partition functions are approximations which seem to hold for large particle numbers. The interaction (or scattering approach) does not seem to be limited to particle number (at least for deriving the number distribution). In previous notes, we have tried to map the scattering approach directly to $M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)$. The maximization of this quantity is approximated (by using large m_i) by the canonical partition function which in turn is approximated by the grand canonical partition function. Alternatively, however, the scattering approach may be used to define a Kaniadakis entropy which leads directly, using $E-TS+uN$, to a grand canonical partition function. In neither case, does one use an explicit large N approximation, although $E-TS+uN$ is tied to thermodynamics, which may implicitly assume large N . Thus, a scattering or interaction approach may be more direct and not rely on as many approximations as partition function approaches.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that interaction arguments (similar to time reversal two body elastic scattering arguments) may be applied to the quantum case of electrons in an atom. This approach seems to bypass the use of $\text{Tr}(\exp(-\text{Hamiltonian}/T))$. We find, however, that the canonical $\exp(-E_i/T)$ weights for each determinant squared may differ from weights used in the reaction approach. We also suggest that partition function approaches may only approximately match the reaction-scattering approach for large particle numbers, but that the reaction-scattering approach may apply to small or large numbers of particles as it only uses averages.

References

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